

Agro2Circular

D7.16. Report on potential for adoption and scale-up potential

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List of abbreviations

BAU – Business as Usual (solution)

CEAP – Circular Economy Action Plan

CSO – Civil Society Organisations

eLCC – Environmental Life Cycle Costing

FIAB – Federación Española de Industrias de Alimentación y Bebidas

LCA – Life Cycle Assessment

LCSA – Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment

PEF – Product Environmental Footprint

SAT – Self Assessment tool

SDG – Sustainable Development Goals

SO-LCA – Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment

WS – Workshop

1 Executive summary <abstract>

D.7.16. Report on potential for adoption and scale-up potential represents one of the final outcomes related to tasks 7.6 and 7.7 which aimed to ensure the replicability and scalability of the A2C systemic solution by studying replication potential in two European regions, validating the A2C multidimensional model and Self-Assessment Tool (SAT) by cross-fertilising with other clusters, thereby fostering adoption of the A2C model.

In line with these objectives, this report presents evidence that A2C technologies offer opportunities for both replication and scaling across diverse contexts. After 42 months of project implementation, the analysis demonstrates clear pathways for territorial transfer and cross-sector application through replication studies in Lombardy and Lithuania regions, stakeholder consultations, and practical implementation insights from the Murcia Circular Action Plan.

The report documents how the A2C approach maximises circular economy potential through proven technological developments with strong market viability, comprehensive evaluation frameworks that support adoption decisions, and strategic integration with the multidimensional model and SAT working synergistically.

Key evidence supporting the scalability potential includes successful validation across diverse regional contexts, demonstrated cross-sector applicability, and strong stakeholder endorsement gathered through EU-wide workshops and targeted consultations. The multidimensional model and SAT emerge as critical enablers for systematic replication, providing organisations with practical tools to assess readiness, identify optimisation opportunities, and implement the A2C solution effectively.

The findings synthesised in this report—spanning technological evaluations, replication case studies, stakeholder feedback, and regional scaling experiences—offer actionable insights and policy recommendations for organisations and regions seeking to implement or scale circular economy solutions.

2 Introduction

In the Agro2Circular project, replication and scale-up are of the utmost importance. These principles are incorporated into two of the initiative's three objectives and are the focal point of one specific work package, along with other interdisciplinary activities. On the one hand, project objective two aimed to provide to the A2C technological solution the circular systemic approach by building a multidimensional model enabling the solution territorial deployment and its replication and scalability. It entailed to construct the multidimensional model and foster its replicability and scalability together with the validations of the applicability of the model and the tools delivered, through cross-fertilization with other agrifood clusters and relevant stakeholders. On the other hand, project objective three aimed at maximizing project impacts and facilitating A2C systemic solution replication & scalability and it entailed to engage in cooperation and mobilization of all relevant stakeholders at local and EU levels among other relevant activities. Focusing on the operationalisation of the mentioned objectives, WP7 “A2C systemic solution adoption, replication and scalability” is where the majority of the efforts have been made, and specific tasks have been implemented to achieve these goals. Task 7.6. “*Italian/Lithuanian Region replication case*” and Task 7.7. “*Validation of the A2C multidimensional model through cross-fertilization with other clusters*” are the concrete tasks nurturing this deliverable.

It is worth noting that under the approach followed in this project, replication and scaling are two pathways of an interconnected process. This interconnection stems from the project's integrated methodology, where replication provides the horizontal expansion across different territories and contexts, while scaling delivers the vertical growth in adoption and impact. The multidimensional model and self-assessment tool serve both purposes simultaneously – enabling adaptation to new regions (replication) while identifying opportunities for wider application and increased adoption (scaling). Concretely, the Murcia case and the results presented in *D.7.11. A2C circular Action Plan report* stands out for the scaling up part and the Lombardy and Lithuania cases, with D.7.16 & D.7.17, corresponding to the replication of the A2C solution. This deliverable aims to make this interconnectedness clear. In the three cases, technological/ systemic/ supply chain solutions, and the

multidimensional model and the strategic analysis have been taken into account to deliver the final results.

The document commences with an introduction that contextualises the work presented within the broader scope of the project. Secondly, the A2C approach is presented. This section is composed of different subsections where relevant information on A2C activities towards replicability and scalability is presented. The initial section of this part is dedicated to the critical evaluation of the primary technological advancements that have been achieved within the scope of the project. This is followed by a summary of the primary evaluation results, which are analysed in order to draw relevant conclusions on what the sustainability (*considering environmental, economic and social dimensions*) assessment results can tell us about replication and scale-up. Section 3.3 addresses the multidimensional model and self-assessment tool and its relationship with the deliverable topic. The following two subsections present the main results and lessons learned from the two A2C replication cases, followed by the main insights from the Murcia case. Section 3.6. presents the principal outcomes of the workshop conducted with other EU agro-food clusters and regions to assess the replication and scalability of the model. The deliverable concludes with a battery of policy recommendations (section 4) and final conclusions (section 5).

3 A2C Approach: maximizing CE potential

A2C's approach to replication and scaling-up has been centred on developing a multidimensional model through co-creation with engaged stakeholders, complemented by a self-assessment tool that enables stakeholders and clusters to evaluate their initial conditions and define implementation roadmaps (see *D.7.10. A2C systemic solution model and self-assessment tool*). The strategy employed a bottom-up methodology, actively involving Civil Society Organizations (CSO) and different stakeholders while systematically identifying and analysing barriers affecting circular solutions. The solution's validation included two specific replication cases: one in Italy's Lombardy region (*for more information on this replication case see deliverable D.7.17. Lombardy Action Plan*), a significant player in the agrifood sector, and another in Lithuania's NUTS-2 region (*for more information on this replication case see deliverable D.7.18. Lithuania NUTS-2 Action Plan*). Moreover, its validation went beyond the replication cases. Its validation also focused on the scaling up by developing a Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) for the Murcia Region and included in *D.7.11. A2C circular Action Plan report*.

To support implementation, A2C also have developed practical guidelines, policy and financing recommendations, training packages, and documented case studies, facilitating knowledge transfer between stakeholders (see *deliverables D.7.4 Community based innovation schemes, D.7.13 Policy Briefs (Final), D.7.15 Financing recommendations (Final), D.8.7 Toolkit of guidelines and training materials (Final)*). The approach extends its reach through collaboration with major European initiatives, including the CCRI initiative, European Institute of Innovation and Technology, and various European platforms focused on circular economy, clusters, and urban development (*for more information on the A2C network please see D.7.3. Public Engagement Strategy & Summary of Activities and Results (Final)*).

Through these comprehensive measures, A2C aimed to maximize adoption potential while supporting EU policy objectives aligned with the European Green Deal, Circular Economy Action Plan, Bioeconomy Strategy, and European Industrial Strategy. Cross-validation has been ensured through engagement with different European agrifood clusters via workshops, ensuring the model's applicability across diverse European contexts.

In the following sections a brief description of the technological developments carried out in the project and the main evaluation results related with this technology are presented, as well as the link with the multidimensional model and self-assessment tool. These sections are followed by the Lombardy, NUTS-2 and Murcia cases to illustrate how the technology developments and systemic approach have been incorporated within their strategic plans¹. Finally, the main results of the cross-validation workshop carried out in the last months of the project are presented.

3.1. Technological developments and their potential in the market

Technological developments are at A2C's core. Figure 1 represents the relation between all the different technical solutions developed in the project. These technical solutions are grouped in 10 different demonstrators, which basically treat two different types of waste. On the one hand, **fruit and vegetable waste**, specifically broccoli, apple, cauliflower, citrus (lemon), artichoke and grape waste. On the other hand, **plastic waste**: metallised/multilayer 200-litre bags for the transport of juice concentrates and multilayer films for soil disinfection. These different waste upcycling configures the two main typologies of Value Chains of the project.

WP6 "*Demonstration of the A2C technological solution*" is the work package aimed to integrate physically all the developed technologies at pilot scale in demonstrators in the south of Spain as well as to demonstrate all the technologies in a relevant industrial environment and manufacturing the different A2C prototypes. Moreover, it has set the basis for industrial implementation and to define the A2C business cases, identifying the specific business models and the financial framework. One of the main outputs of this WP is deliverable "D.6.3. *A2C demonstrators*". In this deliverable, information on the demonstrators of the technologies and prototypes of the valorised products at relevant scale and industrial level, to demonstrate A2C solution at TRL6-7, are presented.

¹ In order to avoid repetition, this section will present information strictly linked to the objective of this deliverable. For more information regarding the replication cases see D.7.17 and D.7.18.

Figure 1 A2C technological solution

Each one of the A2C DEMOS² employs different processes and technologies and on some occasions, there are linkages between them. In order to briefly clarify them, below are presented:

Demonstrators for recycling sector:

DEMO1: recycling plant for the upcycling of multilayer/multimaterial flexible packaging (aseptic bags used in the food processing industry) containing aluminium, where several technologies have been developed and integrated; washing line, optical sorting, delamination & aluminium recovery, recycled plastic compounding and enzymatic depolymerisation. Located in Murcia (Spain). End users: Plastic compounding industries.

² For more information on A2C DEMOS, please review *D.6.3. A2C demonstrators*.

Figure 2 DEMO1: Multilayer plastic waste upcycling diagram

Demonstrators for cosmetics, food & nutraceuticals sector

DEMO2: yeast factory for the production of 3 different ingredients for cosmetic formulations. Located in Murcia (Spain). End users: Cosmetic industries.

Figure 3 DEMO2: yeast factory building blocks production diagram

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DEMO3: extraction route 1 (high added value substances from agrifood waste by enzymatic extraction/ultrasound assisted extraction+ purification + stabilisation). Food, nutraceutic, cosmetic formulations. Located in Murcia (Spain). End users: Cosmetic industries and food industries.

DEMO4: Extraction route 2 (high added value extracted substances from agrifood residues by enzymatic hydrolysis assisted extraction + microwave extraction + purification + microencapsulation). Food nutraceutic, cosmetic formulations. Located in Murcia (Spain). End users: Cosmetic industries and food industries.

Figure 4 DEMO3&4: Extraction route based on green hybrid technologies diagram

DEMO5: cell factory. PHBV & Carotenoids production. Located in Murcia (Spain). End users: Cosmetic industries and plastic compounding industries.

Figure 5 DEMO5: Biodegradable plastic from sugar-rich waste diagram

Demonstrators for food packaging sector:

DEMO6: Bioplastic PHBV based compounding. Biodegradable packaging. Located in Murcia (Spain). End users: Plastic transformer.

Figure 6 DEMO6 & (8): Circular solution diagram

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DEMO7: Recycled and recyclable high barrier compounds for food packaging. Located in Murcia (Spain). End users: Plastic transformer.

Demonstrators for agriculture primary sector:

DEMO8: Bioplastics PHBV compounds to use in biodegradable agricultural films. Located in Murcia (Spain). End users: Plastic transformer.

DEMO9: Recycled and recyclable very high barrier compounds for agricultural films. Located in Murcia (Spain). End users: Plastic transformer.

Figure 7 DEMO7&9&2: Circular solution diagram

Demonstrator for Circular Economy Digitalisation:

DEMO10: Data Integration System for the traceability assurance along the value chains and predictive tool support. End users: agrifood sector industries, recycling industries & plastic industries.

Figure 8 DEMO10: A2C data integration system (DIS)

All these technologies, practices and processes are part of the tangible list of results of A2C. However, the technology market readiness varies significantly, ranging from medium-stage developments to fully commercialised solutions.

Green extraction methods, such as ultrasound-assisted and enzymatic hydrolysis with microwave treatment, are being explored for sustainable ingredient production. On one side, even though **ultrasound technology** is already mature, its large-scale application in extraction processes still faces cost and efficiency challenges [1], this technology can be classified as potentially ready. On the other side, **enzymatic hydrolysis** seems to be a good alternative to conventional methods, and it is still at a medium adoption stage.

Meanwhile, some other innovations also remain in their medium adoption stage due to technical and economic barriers. Bioplastic PHBV compounds to use in biodegradable agricultural films and bioplastics PHBV compounds to use in biodegradable food packaging are promising alternatives to conventional plastics. However, despite growing interest in sustainable materials, their high production costs and mechanical limitations hinder widespread adoption [2].

Regarding yeast building blocks production even though it has been demonstrated to have great potential, it has still a long path to achieve being an economic option [3] in the market, for this reason it is classified as potentially ready technology.

Finally, the **data integration system** represents a unique case, due to its wide-spread use across multiple sectors, one of them the agrifood sector. While the market for data-driven

solutions is expanding [4], integration into the agrifood sector is becoming more and more demanded in order to optimise certain processes. Even though these systems are already market mature, globalisation has overpriced these data services, putting pressure on the farmers [5]. In summary, while some technologies are nearing commercialisation, others require further development and investment before achieving full market adoption. The continuous evolution of these innovations, driven by regulatory policies, consumer demand, and technological improvements, will shape their future integration into the European economy.

It also needs to be mentioned that the technologies developed within the A2C framework have significant potential for application beyond their original scope. These innovations could be valuable in various recycling streams, such as other plastic types or textile recycling, where they could help track fabric composition and verify sustainable material sourcing. E-waste management represents another promising application area, where these technologies could ensure responsible handling and recycling of electronics and hazardous materials. Additionally, given the construction sector's paramount importance across Europe, applying A2C technologies to construction waste valorisation presents another strategic opportunity for cross-sector exploitation³.

3.2. Evaluation insights linked to adoption and replicability

Life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA) is a tool to assess sustainability from a life cycle perspective. This framework consists of an integrated approach that incorporates environmental, economic, and social aspects into the same technological system [6]. In A2C, this approach was utilised to evaluate the developed technologies. From the various existing methodologies to apply this framework, the environmental component followed the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology and Environmental Footprint (EF) impact assessment method developed by the European Commission, the economic component employed environmental Life Cycle Costing (eLCC), and the social component implemented Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA). For more information on the evaluation results, please consult D.7.7. *Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C*

³ For more information on the possible exploitation pathways, please consult D.6.5. *A2C business cases*.

circularity monitoring (Final) and *D.7.9. Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (Final)*.

The first goal of the **LCA** was to detect which processes or life cycle stages have the highest contribution to the A2C systems' environmental impacts. This was done using hotspot analysis. The second goal was to benchmark the environmental performance of the A2C circular solution against a functionally equivalent linear solution. The purpose of combining the benchmarking and hotspot analysis was to identify what are the aspects of the novel A2C system which need to be possibly improved to reach the level of sustainability as the more developed benchmark products. Regarding the **eLCC**, the aim was to compare the associated economic and environmental costs (eLCC) over the entire life cycle of the innovative solutions which have been tested, in comparison with the Business as usual (BAU) solution.

The analysis focused on two primary systems: agrifood and plastic waste, examining multiple demonstration cases across various scales. Key findings highlighted the critical importance of energy consumption and material utilisation in the processes. On the agrifood part of eLCA one of the findings was that the production of process chemicals and electricity contributed substantially to all impact categories analysed, with chemicals used in demos 5, 8, and 6 showing particularly significant impacts across most categories. Despite the current limitations in data scale and comprehensiveness, the research provides a foundational understanding that points to clear pathways for technological improvement.

Concerning the economic results, the sensitivity analysis carried out revealed a promising potential at a larger scale. Overall costs could be reduced by up to 60%, suggesting significant economic viability with increased production volumes. Moreover, one of the most encouraging findings is the economic competitiveness in specific sectors. For instance, in plastic waste recycling, the A2C solution demonstrated a 21% cost advantage compared to conventional alternatives. In agrifood system, while initial costs appeared higher, the solution offered superior product concentration (phenolic extract) and better quality than the benchmark product.

To sum up, the data indicates that while the A2C system offers innovative approaches to waste valorisation, it currently requires an optimised production scale to reach both environmental and economic competitiveness compared to conventional alternatives. The high dependence on chemical inputs, energy requirements, and equipment costs presents

opportunities for optimisation through process improvements, chemical circulation, and renewable energy integration to enhance overall sustainability performance. On the economic side, several costs are affected by the demo testing medium scale, which prevents the recycling process from achieving a higher level of efficiency. Another example is that since equipment cost, and partly maintenance, are influenced by the demo testing medium scale, and the overall eLCC cost of the recycled plastic pellet would certainly be reduced with a higher scale of yearly production. The data indicates that while A2C technologies show promise for Circular Economy applications, selective and strategic replication with continued optimisation would yield better outcomes than direct replication of the current system configuration.

So, in order to enhance technological replication and scalability, it should be prioritised the replication of processes with more favourable environmental and economic profiles rather than a full system replication, given the varying performance across the demos. Moreover, other recommendation would be to focus research and development efforts on reducing chemical inputs and increasing energy efficiency in high-impact processes, given the results of both evaluations.

The social assessment of the A2C organisations (**SO-LCA**) has derived in a series of conclusions about their performance and contribution to social sustainability. By highlighting positive social performance indicators, the assessment provides a comprehensive view of the organisations' social contributions that can serve as a catalyst for future adoption and scaling of the A2C solution. These indicators are linked to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and demonstrate the organisations' commitment to ethical and responsible practices. For instance, the organisations showed exemplary performance in critical social dimensions: no reported instances of forced labour, zero sexual harassment incidents, absence of anti-competitive behaviour sanctions, and full compliance with tax obligations. Moreover, each organisation demonstrated positive contributions across the five stakeholder groups evaluated.

These social performance insights are not merely descriptive but serve as a strategic driver for the A2C solution's broader adoption. By showcasing the organisations' positive social impact, the assessment provides a compelling narrative that can help reduce barriers to implementation and encourage replication of the A2C approach in other contexts.

3.3. Relation with the multidimensional model and the SAT

Multidimensional systems change has been widely recognised as necessary to address some of our most complex social and ecological challenges, and thus, the cultivation of innovation in technological niches alone will be insufficient [7]. A2C addresses this critical gap by addressing systematically various barriers to circular solutions, including socioeconomic, environmental, regulatory, and financial factors. At its core, A2C introduces a comprehensive Circular Economy model that enables territories to adopt, replicate, and scale sustainable, regenerative, and inclusive solutions. This model not only strengthens urban and regional economies but also provides practical tools for all stakeholders—from citizens to industry leaders, policymakers, and the academic community—to advance circular practices. This model is merely the framework. Within A2C, a self-assessment tool has also been developed and digitalised to assist cities and regions in **adopting, replicating and scaling** the A2C solution.

The primary objective of the A2C model is to define the key dimensions and elements that a region (or city) should consider becoming circular, especially within the context of the agrifood industry. The model covers eight dimensions: environmental, socioeconomic, governance, policy and regulatory, funding & financial, technology and R&D, standardisation and capacity building. Each dimension is characterised by specific elements that are crucial for achieving circularity.

Figure 9 A2C self-assessment tool in the DIS tool

The A2C SAT (<https://sat.agro2dis.eu/>) is designed to evaluate the readiness of a region or city to adopt the A2C circular economy model. It is intended for use by regions and cities to qualitatively self-assess and identify key areas for improvement in their

circular economy initiatives. The A2C SAT directly utilises the dimensions and elements

defined by the A2C model. It transforms these elements into Likert scales, enabling regions and cities to assess their level of implementation and effectiveness in deploying circular economy policies. In order to facilitate its use and adoption in other regions and cities, the SAT has been digitalised and included in the DIS tool (see Figure 10). As it can be seen, the structure of the tool is very simple. It is composed of three main pages:

- **Instructions:** this page provides guidance on how to use the tool effectively.
- **Evaluation:** each of the eight dimensions follows the same structure. Every dimension consists of multiple elements, each accompanied by an explanation, assessment hints, and a Likert scale for evaluation. The results are automatically saved throughout the form's completion and can be accessed on the "Results" page.
- **Results:** once its assessment per dimension is submitted, the results are displayed in this page accompanied by a series of general recommendations by dimension to inspire and guide users in further steps of implementing CE.

Figure 10 SAT results display: environmental and socioeconomic dimension examples

The SAT serves as a pivotal instrument in facilitating the adoption, replication, and scale-up of both the multidimensional model and technological solutions within the A2C project. The SAT functions as a diagnostic and planning mechanism that enables stakeholders to evaluate their specific context and develop customized implementation pathways.

It allows clusters and stakeholders to evaluate their initial conditions and determine how these unique circumstances may affect the implementation process of circular economy practices (*including the adoption of the technologies or processes developed in the A2C*

project). Moreover, this tool facilitates the creation of customised roadmaps for implementation, based on the assessment findings. It emphasises the needs and strengths of the territory, providing a foundation for a systematic approach to adopting circular economy practices.

Another key mechanism to facilitate adoption, replication and scale-up is that the SAT is intended to connect assessment outcomes to practical resources developed through the A2C project. This includes policy recommendations, financing options, training packages, and documented best practices that are allocated in A2C webpage ([Resources – Agro2Circular](#)) and correspond to the following deliverables:

- D.7.3. Public Engagement Strategy & Summary of Activities and Results (Final)
- D.7.10. A2C systemic solution model and self assessment tool
- D.7.13. Policy Briefs (Final)
- D.7.15. Financing recommendations (Final)
- D.8.7. Toolkit of guidelines and training materials (Final)
- D.8.10. Contribution to standardization (Final)

This ensures that stakeholders receive guidance that is both theoretically sound and practically applicable.

Furthermore, the cross-validation of the SAT with different European agrifood clusters, regions and cities, enhances its reliability and applicability across diverse European contexts. This validation process ensures that the tool maintains flexibility while providing structured support for implementation across varying conditions.

The SAT ultimately bridges the gap between theoretical models and practical implementation, accelerating the adoption, replication, and scale-up of circular solutions across Europe.

3.4. A2C replication cases: Lombardy and Lithuania regions

A2C demonstration entailed a strong focus on facilitating the circular technical solution early adoption and further replication & scalability. This was achieved through a systemic approach based on the identification and analysis of challenges, enablers and barriers hampering the deployment of the solution not only at A2C cluster level but also at national and European level. In this sense, and in the framework of Task 7.6, the project has involved two specific replication cases, in the Italian region of Lombardy, one of the major players on

the agrifood sector and in the NUTS-2 Baltic region from Lithuania. Concretely, task 7.6 aimed to demonstrate A2C's replication potential through the development of specific implementation plans for circular economy business models in both regions, encompassing contextual analysis of agrifood residues, strategic stakeholder engagement, multidimensional territorial assessment according to the A2C model, and development of tailored circular business models to ensure readiness for post-project implementation. The main outputs of this task have been two deliverables (D.7.17⁴ & D.7.18⁵) that present the key conclusions of the activities undertaken by these two regions and their capacity for adopting the A2C solution. The partners responsible for this initiative have been TCA, representing the Lombardy region, and LPK, representing Lithuania:

- **Tecnoalimenti (TCA)** is as a non-profit research consortium of 30 food sector industries and one financial institution, Intesa San Paolo, as trustee of ministerial funds. Its member industries account for about 12% of Italian food sales. They have a wide experience in networking industries (large and SMEs) for research activities, due to its institutional function of bridging industry and research players. Further, TCA participated/participates to food chain projects with a specific role of carrying out studies, training activities, steering and animating Industrial Platforms, thanks to its wide experience in approaching food SMEs.
- The **Lithuanian Confederation of Industrialists (LPK)** is a major business association in Lithuania which represents the interests of industrialists and employers. LPK is an independent, non-political organization that represents public interests of all business groups in Lithuania. LPK unites 50 trade and seven regional business associations with over 3000 major business and manufacturing enterprises of the country, as well as 26 largest non-associated enterprises and corporations. LPK members include most Lithuanian production enterprises, banks, trading companies, representative offices of foreign firms, research institutes, and educational establishments.

Deliverable D.7.17 presents a comprehensive structure presenting the **replication analysis and action plan for the Lombardy region**. In the case of the Lombardy region, the analysis has been focused on two main lines of replication: (i) systemic approach to Agro2Circular value chains replicability and (ii) multidimensional replicability analysis according to the

⁴ D7.17. *Lombardy Action Plan (Report-PU; TCA, M42; Related Task 7.6). Synthesis report describing the cluster CEAP (Circular Economy action Plan) for the deployment of circular systemic solutions within Lombardy Region.*

⁵ D7.18. *NUTS-2 Lithuania Action Plan (Report-PU; LPK, M42; Related Task 7.6). Synthesis report describing the cluster CEAP (Circular Economy action Plan) for the deployment of circular systemic solutions within Nuts-2 Lithuania region.*

Agro2Circular model. The cross-cutting element of both replicability lines is the involvement of regional stakeholders in the discussion of the A2C systemic solution.

Document D7.17 provides a comprehensive framework for replicating systemic solutions from Murcia to Lombardy, focusing on circular value chains that valorise agrifood waste. The study combines detailed territorial analysis with technological, environmental, and economic evaluations to identify suitable business models for Lombardy's specific context. Concurrently, A2C's multidimensional model was applied through a collaborative co-creation approach involving regional stakeholders to assess Lombardy's readiness for circular transition across eight CE dimensions, culminating in a CEAP. The document resulted from robust consortium collaboration among TCA (task leader), KVC (multidimensional model), UB (economic assessments), and VTT (environmental assessments), with additional cross-fertilization through comparison with LPK's replicability study in Lithuania and alignment on technological aspects with partners CTNC, SSICA, and DMC for horticultural waste valorisation.

Key findings⁶

Due to the lack of data systematization on waste generation at regional level, a contextual study was conducted on the amounts and types of residues within Lombardy agrifood industry. This work was highly relevant not only for the A2C replication but also at a strategic level for the Lombardy Region.

Moreover, after an analysis of the potential economic and market value of horticultural wastes, the value chains of grapes and apples were selected for the application of the A2C technological model and replicability assessment. As for the technological maturity for replication, the regions show great technological maturity both for polyphenols and fibre extraction step; nutraceutical and cosmetic sectors were identified for industrial synergies and for the definition of the new value chain implementing A2C technological solution. The challenges identified are related to logistics aspects and extracts specifications.

Concerning the Circular Business Models (CBM), two have been identified and developed in Lombardy for the application of the new value chain implementing A2C technological solution.

⁶ More results are presented in D.7.17

The multidimensional regional analysis, according to the A2C model, was mainly based on feedback from the working group involving key public stakeholders and targeted interviews with private stakeholders. Furthermore, additional relevant information and evaluations were obtained from: (i) contextual study with specific reference to the circular value chains of horticultural waste and agro plastic, (ii) targeted desk research on specific dimensions or elements of the CE, (iii) previous experiences and knowledge within the TCA research team and its related industrial network.

The multidimensional analysis shows that Lombardy is ready for the circular transition thanks to the great technological maturity and the great sensitivity of the citizens. Evaluating the 8 dimensions and the 33 elements impacting on the Circular Economy it emerges that in Lombardy best dimensions are socio-economic dimension and governance dimension while the worst dimension is the standardization. In line with the multidimensional and holistic approach to the circular transition, the key actors for the implementation of an effective and efficient CEAP were identified according to the quintuple helix model. Likewise specific policy recommendations transversal to the individual dimensions and elements analysed were pointed out: they are mainly related to active engagement of all stakeholders and key actors and to the public financial support.

As a result of the A2C replicability activities, a roadmap towards circular systems has been developed in line with regional, national and European strategies. It identifies 5 key objectives and emphasises interdisciplinary cooperation and collaboration between science and practice.

Deliverable D.7.18 presents a comprehensive structure presenting the **replication analysis and action plan for the NUTS-2 Baltic region**. The replication analysis is based on a region characterisation and a context analysis based on the A2C Multidimensional Model and using the Self-Assessment tool. The document incorporates detailed supply and value chain analyses to evaluate and validate the feasibility of technological solution adoption within the regional context. The deliverable culminates with business models and a detailed implementation roadmap, providing stakeholders with a pragmatic and achievable pathway for deploying this innovative circular economy vision. This final section translates theoretical frameworks into actionable steps, ensuring the plan's viability within the specific regional parameters of the Baltic NUTS-2 territory.

A number of activities were undertaken in order to elaborate the CEAP presented in D.7.18. In summary, the following activities were carried out: the amounts and types of regional agrifood industry residue were analysed, as well as the industrial synergies identified. Furthermore, a new value chain was defined for the implementation of the A2C technological solution. To achieve this, relevant stakeholders were involved through public engagement activities. A self-assessment exercise was carried out based on the A2C Multidimensional Model in order to identify barriers, challenges, enablers and facilitators. Knowledge exchange with international partners and also with key stakeholders within the region was also undertaken. Specific business models and an action plan for the realisation of the identified activities to boost the transition towards CE were defined and developed.

Key findings⁷:

Comparing Lithuania with Italy and Murcia, Lithuania represents a distinct climate area with comparatively lower population and disparities in economic performance between regions. Moreover, lower recycling and secondary raw materials solutions were developed, and has considerably lower circular material use rate. Also, analysing the Lithuania's NUTS 2 regions, it has been highlighted the regional fragmentation and different governance models along the regions, which made that in particular dimensions (CE governance, policies and regulations) the analysis is carried out at national level since same conditions applies to both regions.

Analysing the agrifood sector was of paramount importance taking into account the project thematic. Lithuania has a strong agricultural industry, one among the fastest growing in the EU however, A2C crops represent a small share in the total production. Thus, to satisfy domestic needs, significant amounts of fruits and vegetables are being imported. As for the food manufacturing sector (food production and processing and preserving fruit and vegetables), it is a growing sector, but it represents a small share of the total activity, besides further development is dependent of the availability of raw materials. In terms of business structure, there are comparatively many farms of a small size in Lithuania, while the level of cooperation in the Lithuanian agrifood sector is relatively low, which can be a challenge for the CE development. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) also dominate in food

⁷ More details are presented in D.7.18.

manufacturing sector, but larger companies generate most of the total value added of this Lithuanian industry.

Several enabling conditions were identified by stakeholders in order to adopt CE, namely the improvement of communication to improve coordination among stakeholders, the reduction of bureaucracy barriers, also the identification and definition of a clear responsible entity that centralises and coordinates all the activities related to CE. The need to overcome the investment gap for innovation was also highlighted and the cooperation between science, business, government and society requested.

Another finding was that the biowaste management system in Lithuania is already highly efficient, thanks to the use of methods to handle waste in a cost-effective and sustainable manner. However, it requires specialised equipment and substantial investment and given the small quantity of available waste the compounds isolation is not viable. Nevertheless, the technologies proposed by A2C for the extraction of fibres and phenols represent a scalable solution, as by focusing on these innovations, cost-effective and sustainable industrial processes for the circular approach can be developed.

As for the plastic area, Lithuania stands out as a leader in recycling PET bottles. Notwithstanding this, the optimisation of the recycling of other types of plastic still remains a challenge. The solution to this problem might be A2C technologies albeit; while promising, these breakthroughs require further time, funding, and refinement to scale up effectively.

In general, and based on the materials availability, it was stated that the plastic waste in agriculture seems more promising to replicate, even though there is a need to change the Lithuanian business models in order to replicate the A2C solution.

All things considered, a CEAP was developed focusing on the LPK community. The proposed action agenda to facilitate the replication of the A2C systemic solution in Lithuania covers actions in the socioeconomic, policy and regulatory, financial, and standardisation areas. In order to replicate A2C solutions in Lithuania's NUTS 2 regions, it is essential to consider the fragmentation of Lithuania's agrifood sector and the need for tailored technological integrations. As Lithuania currently has a fragmented approach to the bioeconomy, clearer guidelines and strategic approaches provided in the current study are very useful for exploiting the potential of this area more effectively.

3.4.1. Lessons learned

TCA and LPK successfully demonstrated the replicability of A2C solutions through the development of targeted plans tailored to specific territorial characteristics. The implementation encompassed both the systemic solutions and the multidimensional model, with adaptation to local contexts.

The assessment identified two major **strengths facilitating solution replicability**. First, the territoriality of value chains created strong connections between solutions and

Image 1 A2C replication cases

local resources, facilitating logistics management and increasing collaboration and trust along value chains. Second, the extraction technology demonstrated remarkable versatility, requiring only minor modifications to accommodate various agricultural waste sources while maintaining efficiency and effectiveness.

Regarding **impact and lessons learned**, the multidimensional analysis conducted in both regions revealed several key factors essential for successful circular transition. Close collaboration among science, business, and government sectors proved fundamental in both territories. The active engagement of stakeholders created shared understanding of circular opportunities, facilitated knowledge transfer across sectors, built consensus around implementation priorities, and established networks that sustained momentum beyond initial implementation. This multi-stakeholder approach overcame traditional sectoral barriers to innovation that might otherwise impede CE development.

Public financial support emerged as another crucial mechanism for CE advancement. Financial mechanisms enabled research and technological innovation that might otherwise be cost-prohibitive, reduced financial risk for early adopters of circular practices, and created incentives that overcame market barriers. Additionally, public funding supported educational

programs that built necessary skills and expertise while financing demonstration projects that showcased viability to hesitant stakeholders.

Both regions identified education and training programs as essential components of successful transition.

Results from A2C replicability will empower TCA to advance circular culture in Lombardy by providing decision-makers with concrete technical data, including agricultural waste generation estimates. The project offers multidimensional analyses of current regional circularity status while facilitating holistic perspectives shared among diverse stakeholders, creating evidence-based frameworks for policy intervention.

Lithuania approached implementation differently through a bottom-up approach focused on the LPK community cluster. The country developed specialised plans aligned with Lithuania's NUTS 2 regional characteristics, creating findings that directly contribute to Lithuania's Bioeconomy Strategy development while demonstrating how sector-specific interventions can inform national policy.

The replication experience suggests several promising future directions, including extension to additional case studies, particularly in "*green banana*" countries with significant agricultural waste challenges. Other opportunities include valorisation of results through trans-regional cooperation initiatives, development of international partnerships to scale successful interventions, and creation of knowledge exchange networks to continuously refine and improve methodologies. Integration with broader sustainability frameworks beyond agricultural sectors represents another valuable direction for future work.

3.5. Scaling A2C at regional level: lessons learned from Murcia Circular Action Plan

This section is based on deliverable *D.7.11. A2C Circular Action Plan report* led by AGRIFOOD. Within this document, a CEAP for the agrifood sector in the region of Murcia is presented, being the practical outcome of the A2C solution scale up. The document includes the actions that can be implemented in the Region of Murcia and that could be extrapolated to other regions for the development of circular solutions in the agrifood industry.

The report's key findings on scaling up are presented below:

1. **Resource optimisation is critical for scaling:** starting a job from scratch takes more time and resources than grouping efforts in actions that are already consolidated. Scaling efforts should build upon existing initiatives rather than creating entirely new programs.
2. **Financial and human resource constraints limit adoption:** Despite many solutions being available in the market, not all companies have access to them due to the necessary investments in terms of financial and human resources, as well as time. This has been identified as a barrier for scaling up the A2C solution.
3. **Multidisciplinary expertise is necessary:** For successful scaling, a multidisciplinary working group specialised in the subject is needed to establish priorities and review implementation points.
4. **Self-assessment tools facilitate replication:** The SAT developed within A2C is a useful tool for diagnosing improvement areas before scaling circular solutions to new regions.
5. **Communication barriers impact scaling speed:** According to AGRIFOOD research, there have been concepts difficult to understand by stakeholders, suggesting that simplified, adapted language is necessary for wider adoption.
6. **Quadruple helix collaboration accelerates scaling:** Facilitating meeting points to discuss ideas among members of the quadruple helix is the most effective way to implement circular economy solutions at scale.
7. **Systemic approach required:** The conclusion states that successful scaling requires a multi-faceted approach that integrates financial incentives, regulatory support, stakeholder collaboration, and knowledge dissemination, in line with A2C approach.
8. **Resource allocation for R&D is a prerequisite:** it is needed to allocate R&D resources in order to implement these types of solutions, however many companies according to AGRIFOOD report lack this prerequisite, indicating a need for support structures to enable scaling.
9. **Knowledge sharing prevents duplication:** the work done in A2C with deliverables D.7.11, D.7.16 and D.7.17, serves as tools for avoiding duplications and optimising the resources across multiple entities, which is essential for efficient scaling.

To sum up, while significant barriers were encountered throughout the implementation process, the comprehensive tools, methodologies, and materials developed within the A2C project can equip other regions to anticipate and overcome these challenges more efficiently. By leveraging these resources, future adopters can not only avoid the identified barriers, but also strategically reinforce the enabling factors that accelerate the transition to a circular economy in their respective agrifood sectors.

3.6. Comprehensive Analysis of A2C Model Replication and Scalability Potential: EU stakeholders' workshop

The A2C project implemented a strategic approach to cross-fertilization activities, specifically targeting Task 7.1 (*Public Engagement and community-based schemes for sustainable systemic circular economy*), 7.5 (*Multidimensional model for adoption, replicability and scalability of A2C systemic solution at regional and EU level*) & 7.7 (*Validation of the A2C multidimensional model through cross-fertilization with other clusters*). These interconnected tasks encompassed public engagement for sustainable CE schemes, development of a multidimensional model for A2C solution adoption, and validation of the model through inter-cluster collaboration.

In line with the project's comprehensive stakeholder engagement and European outreach strategies, a dedicated EU Stakeholder Panel was established. This panel, was constituted together with a Regional Stakeholder Panel, ensuring a multi-layered approach to project insights and interactions throughout the project's duration.

Researchers and interested parties seeking detailed information about the engagement process can refer to three key deliverable documents: *D.7.1 Public Engagement (Draft)*, *D.7.2 Public Engagement Strategy & Summary of Activities and Results (Status Report)*, and *D.7.3 Public Engagement Strategy & Summary of Activities and Results (Final)*. These documents provide comprehensive documentation of the project's engagement initiatives, methodologies, and outcomes.

The most recent collaborative endeavour was a workshop organised by Kveloce (KVC), the University of Valencia (UVEG) and the European Association of Development Agencies (EURADA) on Friday, 17th of January 2025. **This workshop aimed at exploring the**

scalability and replicability of the Agro2Circular (A2C) multidimensional model across different regions, cities and clusters.

More than 25 organisations were invited by EURADA & KVC to join the workshop and provide insights on the model replication and scalable potential. The list of institutions invited went beyond the A2C EU stakeholder panel in order to ensure the participation and insights of enough European institutions and taking advantage of the EURADA extensive network of regional development agencies. The final list of attendees is provided below:

- Project s.a.s. (Consultancy Company, Italy)
- PNRR, Regione Umbria (Regional Development Agency, Italy)
- RDA Centru (Regional Development Agency, Romania)
- FIAB (Industrial Cluster, Spain)
- Agrotransilvania Cluster (Industrial Cluster, Romania)
- RDA NW (Regional Development Agency, Romania)
- ADR Nord-Vest (Regional Development Agency, Romania)
- FILSE (Technical entity that provides support to the Regione Liguria)

To optimise workshop preparation and participants engagement, the attendees were provided with a detailed summary of the Multidimensional Model rationale and dimensions elements (see Annex 1) and the SAT pdf for their preliminary review (see Figure 11).

Also, to ensure a focused and productive discussion, a pre-workshop survey was prepared and shared with the attendees. This strategic approach was intended to guide participant reflections and concentrate the workshop dialogue on the survey's analytical findings, thereby maximizing the efficiency and relevance of the collaborative session.

Figure 11 Workshop materials

Workshop Materials - A2C Model. Policy Strategies for Circular Agrifood Solutions

<p>Agenda</p> <p>9:00–9:05h: Welcome and Introductions 9:05–9:15h: Overview of the A2C Model and SAT 9:15–10:25h: Presentation of Survey Results & Guided Discussion 10:25–10:30h: Wrap-Up and Closing</p> <p>		
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3.6.1. Survey respondents: sample characterisation

The number of respondents was 7, that came from different institutions across the EU:

- North-East Regional Development Agency
- Ingredalia
- AgroTransilvania Cluster
- North-East Regional Development Agency
- FOOD FOR LIFE-SPAIN
- Project HUB 360
- ProjectHUB360

Respondents represent a variety of organisations primarily focused on regional development, agrifood innovation, and collaborative projects. Notably, some entities are from Romania—such as the North-East Regional Development Agency and AgroTransilvania Cluster—while others, like FOOD FOR LIFE-SPAIN and Ingredalia, are Spanish. Overall, this group encompasses both public bodies (regional development agencies) and private or semi-private initiatives (clusters, companies, and project hubs). The 57% of respondents who knew the project before the WS and the 43% who did not. The SAT was created with the aim of helping regions and cities all over Europe to develop their CEAPs or transition strategies, fostering the adoption of CE. The 71% of the WS

participants declared that in their region/city it is in place a CEAP or CE strategy, while the 29% stated that they were unaware of the existence or non-existence of this practice.

3.6.2. Feedback gathered: replicability and scalability of the A2C Model.

Replicability refers to the ability of a CE practice, model, or initiative to be reproduced or adapted by other entities or in different contexts, while maintaining its core benefits and principles. There was a significant degree of agreement in the stakeholders’ responses, as all respondents indicated that the model is **moderately replicable** (see Figure 12). Two of the respondents indicated that they haven’t had enough knowledge of the model, so they voted for the middle answer.

Figure 12 Replicability of the A2C Model: stakeholders' feedback

However, there were slightly more positive evaluations regarding the model's scalability potential (see Figure 13). Factors identified as influencing the scalability of the model included:

- “The level of commitment of the stakeholders”
- “A more active political response is needed.”

These responses might underscore the interdependent

nature of stakeholder engagement and political support in ensuring successful model expansion. The identified factors emphasise the importance of aligning implementation strategies with policy frameworks and securing institutional support at various governance levels.

Interestingly the **SAT tool seems to have generated greater consensus** regarding its adaptability to different regions, with agreement highlighting its flexibility. Overall, it is considered that all dimensions of the SAT tool are useful. The dimensions with higher consensus were the socioeconomic, financial and funding and the innovation and technology dimensions. However, there was **slightly less consensus on the environmental, governance, and standardisation dimensions**.

Figure 14 Adaptability and usefulness of the SAT tool: stakeholders' feedback

In general, it can be concluded that the SAT tool is perceived as useful. Further conclusions of the workshop will be included in section 4 Policy recommendations for scaling and replicating , since the second part of it turned around the discussion of policy measures for the replicability and scalability of the A2C Model.

4. Policy recommendations for scaling and replicating

Agriculture has been the primary source of food for humanity since time immemorial. With the ever-growing global population and the rising demand for food supplies, there has been a transition from traditional agricultural practices to more advanced methods [8]. This section presents key recommendations for enhancing the replication and scalability of A2C solutions⁸, addressing both technical implementations and elements of the multidimensional model (see Table 1). These guidelines aim to facilitate broader adoption across diverse contexts and operational environments and have been obtained and prioritised in the carried-out workshop presented in section 3.6. Comprehensive Analysis of A2C Model Replication and Scalability Potential: EU stakeholders' workshop.

Table 1 Multidimension recommendations: fostering replication and scaling up

	Replicability	Scalability
Environmental dimension	Create permanent working and coordination groups for by-products, with a regional register to facilitate reuse and recycling efforts. Strengthen waste management policies, including the establishment of integrated and decentralised water and waste infrastructures.	Promote product lifetime extension through design for longevity and maintenance of durable goods, reducing waste generation
<i>Rationale: The establishment of permanent working and coordination groups, alongside a regional register for by-products, enhances replicability by providing structured mechanisms that can be easily adapted to different regions. These initiatives ensure systematic collaboration between stakeholders, creating a blueprint that can be replicated in various contexts. Similarly, strengthening waste management policies and developing decentralised infrastructures facilitate scalability by creating resilient and adaptable systems that accommodate increasing waste streams and diverse environmental challenges across regions.</i>		
Socioeconomic dimension	Establish a permanent forum aligned with national efforts to continuously spread Circular Economy culture and best practices.	Support initiatives that focus on employment opportunities and the creation of new businesses within the Circular Economy

⁸ As it can be seen, in some cases the recommendations are included in both columns (replicability and scalability). As explained at the beginning of the deliverable, we see both processes as a linked journey, thus some recommendations apply to both pathways.

<p>Utilise gamification and innovative communication strategies to integrate Circular Economy into residents' daily lives and promote active participation.</p>	<p>sector, particularly involving individuals with limited access to the labour market. Implement training programs and disseminate information on the environmental, economic, and social impacts of Circular Economy practices to enhance community engagement and understanding.</p>
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Rationale: The promotion of a permanent forum for Circular Economy awareness aligns with replicability by institutionalising knowledge-sharing mechanisms that other regions can adopt with minimal adaptation. The use of gamification and innovative communication strategies enhances engagement and participation, making it easier for communities to adopt Circular Economy principles. For scalability, supporting employment opportunities and business creation fosters economic resilience, ensuring that as the Circular Economy sector expands, it continues to integrate marginalised groups and generate long-term benefits. The inclusion of training programmes ensures that knowledge diffusion keeps pace with sectoral growth, providing a skilled workforce to sustain Circular Economy initiatives.

Governance dimension

<p>Create regional forums on Circular Economy to bring together diverse stakeholders and foster dialogue and cooperation.</p> <p>Establish a public monitoring platform for green procurement.</p> <p>Implement a Circular Supplier Certification system to give advantages in public procurement processes.</p> <p>Develop policy strategies that promote multi-level governance initiatives, utilising regional policy instruments like the ERDF to align regional strategies with Circular Economy goals and boost participation in circular businesses.</p>	<p>Create regional forums on Circular Economy to bring together diverse stakeholders and foster dialogue and cooperation.</p> <p>Develop policy strategies that promote multi-level governance initiatives, utilising regional policy instruments like the ERDF to align regional strategies with Circular Economy goals and boost participation in circular businesses.</p>
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Rationale: The creation of regional forums for Circular Economy governance supports replicability by establishing a structured dialogue between stakeholders, allowing other regions to model their own governance structures accordingly. The introduction of public monitoring platforms and supplier certification systems further standardises Circular Economy practices, ensuring coherence across different jurisdictions. For scalability, policy strategies leveraging multi-level governance instruments, such as the ERDF, facilitate broader adoption by integrating Circular Economy goals into existing institutional frameworks, ensuring that regional initiatives can seamlessly align with national and European policies.

Policy & Regulatory dimension

<p>Restructure public procurement to prioritise products and services that meet Circular Economy environmental standards, including incentives in contracts to enhance project life cycles.</p>	<p>Simplify and clarify the legislative framework for Circular Economy, including regulation of by-products and end-of-waste criteria, measures against planned obsolescence, and ensuring spare parts availability.</p> <p>Restructure public procurement to prioritise products and services that meet Circular</p>
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Promote pay-as-you-throw systems to discourage waste disposal and encourage recycling and waste reduction.	Economy environmental standards, including incentives in contracts to enhance project life cycles.
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Rationale: The restructuring of public procurement towards Circular Economy standards ensures replicability by setting a precedent for sustainable purchasing criteria that can be adapted across different administrative levels. The introduction of pay-as-you-throw systems provides a proven financial incentive model for waste reduction that can be easily implemented elsewhere. In terms of scalability, simplifying the legislative framework for by-products and end-of-waste criteria eliminates regulatory ambiguities, fostering a more predictable and efficient business environment that facilitates the expansion of Circular Economy solutions at a larger scale.

Funding & Financial dimension

<p>Create new financial instruments tailored for both public administration and businesses to facilitate Circular Economy projects and investments.</p> <p>Ensure access to adequate financial resources by establishing special funds, risk-sharing mechanisms, and financial advisory services to support Circular Economy initiatives.</p>	<p>Provide public funding, subsidies, and financial incentives to support Circular Economy initiatives and drive the transition to a circular economy.</p> <p>Create new financial instruments tailored for both public administration and businesses to facilitate Circular Economy projects and investments.</p>
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Rationale: The creation of tailored financial instruments ensures replicability by offering adaptable funding mechanisms that can be modified to suit different regional and national contexts. Establishing special funds and risk-sharing mechanisms further enhances financial sustainability, making Circular Economy investments more attractive and reducing the financial risks associated with early-stage projects. For scalability, providing subsidies and financial incentives drives widespread adoption, ensuring that businesses and public administrations can transition towards Circular Economy practices without encountering prohibitive upfront costs.

Technology & Innovation dimension

<p>Foster eco-design through targeted training activities and financial incentives to encourage sustainable product development.</p> <p>Stimulate innovation in product chains and Circular Economy entrepreneurship by providing funding, launching challenges, and allocating resources for living labs that test and develop new Circular Economy solutions</p> <p>Implement pilot projects within critical regional value chains to explore and refine Circular Economy practices, leveraging synergies with other funding instruments.</p> <p>Promote changes in industrial fabrication, support the development of green patents, and encourage the growth of high-tech and clean technology industries through dedicated programs and incentives.</p>	<p>Implement pilot projects within critical regional value chains to explore and refine Circular Economy practices, leveraging synergies with other funding instruments.</p> <p>Promote changes in industrial fabrication, support the development of green patents, and encourage the growth of high-tech and clean technology industries through dedicated programs and incentives.</p> <p>Foster the use of traceability tools/digital passports in industry to achieve full value chain visibility.</p>
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Foster the use of traceability tools/digital passports in industry to achieve full value chain visibility.	
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Rationale: The harmonisation of end-of-waste criteria between countries ensures replicability by providing a common regulatory framework that facilitates the exchange of secondary raw materials across borders. The introduction of standardised certification schemes and sustainability labels enhances consumer and business confidence, making it easier to scale Circular Economy initiatives by providing clear market signals and quality assurances. By establishing a recognised framework, new businesses can seamlessly enter the market, ensuring a smoother and more predictable expansion.

Standardisation dimension

Harmonise end-of-waste criteria between countries. Introduce new labels for reusing secondary raw materials in certified building or Circular Economy projects. Establish harmonised certification schemes to support, prove, and verify the statements of sustainability for new products and processes.	Harmonise end-of-waste criteria between countries. Establish harmonised certification schemes to support, prove, and verify the statements of sustainability for new products and processes. Introduce new labels for reusing secondary raw materials in certified building or Circular Economy projects.
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Rationale: The harmonisation of end-of-waste criteria between countries ensures replicability by providing a common regulatory framework that facilitates the exchange of secondary raw materials across borders. The introduction of standardised certification schemes and sustainability labels enhances consumer and business confidence, making it easier to scale Circular Economy initiatives by providing clear market signals and quality assurances. By establishing a recognised framework, new businesses can seamlessly enter the market, ensuring a smoother and more predictable expansion.

Capacity Building dimension

Support educational programs to train scholars in Circular Economy at all educational levels. Implement training activities aimed at different target groups (students, enterprises, public institutions) to create new knowledge and a cultural background favourable to the Circular Economy, ranging from low-qualified to highly qualified workers.	Support educational programs to train scholars in Circular Economy at all educational levels. Implement training activities aimed at different target groups (students, enterprises, public institutions) to create new knowledge and a cultural background favourable to the Circular Economy, ranging from low-qualified to highly qualified workers. Enhance the creation of knowledge exchange and learning networks on Circular Economy.
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Rationale: Supporting educational programmes at all levels ensures replicability by fostering a foundational knowledge base that can be disseminated across different educational institutions and professional sectors. The implementation of targeted training activities ensures that Circular Economy principles are integrated into diverse industries, making it easier to scale practices as demand for skilled professionals grows. Additionally, the development of knowledge exchange networks fosters collaboration between regions, allowing best practices to be rapidly shared and adopted at a larger scale, ensuring that expertise keeps pace with sectoral development.

Source: *elaborated by the authors*

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5. Conclusions

The Agro2Circular project demonstrates significant potential for both replicability and scalability across diverse contexts and sectors. As evidenced by the successful implementation experiences in both Lombardy and Lithuania, A2C solutions can be effectively adapted to different territorial characteristics when proper planning and stakeholder engagement approaches are employed. Also, the CEAP developed by AGROFOOD proved the scaling up potential for the region of Murcia.

The multidimensional model and self-assessment tool developed under WP7 have proven to be a critical tool in this replication and scale up process. By enabling a comprehensive self-assessment of territories across eight circular economy dimensions, the model provides a structured framework for evaluating regional readiness for circular transition. This systematic approach allows stakeholders to identify strengths, weaknesses, and adaptation requirements before implementing A2C solutions, significantly enhancing replication success rates. The model's application in both Lombardy and Lithuania demonstrated its versatility as a diagnostic and planning tool that can be transferred across diverse regional contexts.

The replicability assessment reveals that A2C technologies exist along a range of market readiness. While some innovations stand at the threshold of commercialization, others require additional research and development and investment before achieving full market adoption. This varied maturity landscape presents both challenges and opportunities for scaling. Moreover, the successful replication of these technologies will depend on several key factors that emerged consistently across our replication regions. First, multi-stakeholder collaboration between scientific, business, and governmental sectors provides the necessary ecosystem for adoption and scaling. Second, public financial support mechanisms prove essential for overcoming initial market barriers and de-risking early implementation. Third, comprehensive education and training programs must develop alongside technological implementation to ensure workforce readiness and stakeholder acceptance.

Critically, the scalability of A2C technologies extends well beyond their original agricultural waste context. The innovative approaches developed within the project framework

demonstrate versatility applicable to multiple waste streams, including other plastic types, textiles, electronics, and construction materials. This cross-sector potential significantly expands the impact horizon of A2C innovations and creates multiple pathways for scaling. Furthermore, the example set in *D.7.11 A2C circular Action Plan report* can equip other regions to anticipate and overcome possible challenges identified more efficiently.

In summary, A2C technologies and their systemic approach present robust opportunities for both replication and scaling, with demonstrated pathways for territorial transfer, cross-sector application, and international expansion. The multidimensional model and self-assessment tool provide structured frameworks that significantly enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of these replication and scale up efforts. The continuous evolution of these innovations, driven by regulatory policies, consumer demand, and technological improvements, will ultimately determine the speed and scope of their integration into the broader European and global circular economy landscape.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1. Workshop materials

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Agro2Circular

THE AGRO2CIRCULAR (A2C) MODEL

1. Purpose and methodology

1.1 Purpose and application of the A2C Model

The A2C multidimensional model provides a structured framework to guide regions and cities in adopting circular economy (CE) practices, particularly within the agrifood sector. Designed to assess and strengthen readiness for CE, the model organizes essential factors into eight core dimensions: environmental, socioeconomic, governance, policy and regulatory, funding and finance, technology and R&D, standardisation, and capacity building. The model's practical application lies in its self-assessment tool, which allows public authorities and stakeholders to evaluate existing capacities, identify areas for

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improvement, and formulate actionable Circular Economy Action Plans (CEAPs). Beyond its immediate focus on local and regional entities, the model also serves as a reference for researchers, clusters, and organizations interested in advancing sustainable practices through circular principles.

1.2 Development process and methodology

The A2C model was developed through a multi-step process that combined theoretical foundations with stakeholder inputs. Beginning with a Theory of Change (ToC) review, the team identified the project's goals and mapped the key outputs needed to drive circularity within the agrifood sector. An initial diagnosis of CE challenges specific to the Region of Murcia helped to define relevant factors for each dimension, which were then validated through stakeholder consultations, surveys, and workshops. Subsequent workshops with A2C project partners and broader European panels enabled cross-regional validation and further refinement. Inputs from existing assessment tools and other European CE initiatives contributed to the model's robustness, ensuring its relevance across diverse territorial contexts.

2. Dimensions

2.1 Environmental dimension

The Environmental Dimension focuses on evaluating how a region or city manages resources and environmental impacts in transitioning to a circular economy (CE). Key factors in this dimension include:

1. **Efficient Waste and Water Management:** Assessing the presence of infrastructure and policies that enhance the sustainable use of resources, minimizing waste generation and optimizing water management.
2. **Waste Valorisation Channels:** Evaluating established systems that allow for the transformation of waste materials into useful products or raw materials, closing loops within the local value chain.
3. **Territorial Exploitation Level:** Ensuring that territorial resources are used in a way that does not exceed environmental limits, with managed resource extraction, material transport, and waste circulation.
4. **Land and Biodiversity Degradation:** Considering how well the region mitigates impacts of the linear economy on ecosystems and biodiversity by reducing resource consumption and pollution that degrade habitats.
5. **Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation:** Measuring efforts to assess and reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions across value chains, addressing both mitigation and adaptation needs to achieve sustainability goals.

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2.2 Socioeconomic dimension

The Socioeconomic Dimension evaluates the intersection of economic resilience, social inclusivity, and quality of life in supporting a transition to a circular economy (CE). The factors in this dimension are:

1. **Business Reinvention Capacity:** The ability of local businesses to adapt and innovate sustainably, fostering economic, social, and environmental benefits aligned with CE principles.
2. **Strength of the Production Ecosystem:** The robustness and resilience of the region's economic structure, driven by diverse industries that sustain stability, foster innovation, and adapt to changes.
3. **Professional and Technical Skills:** The readiness of the regional workforce to support the shift from a linear to a circular economy, with an emphasis on relevant skills and expertise.
4. **Trust in the Production System:** The degree of confidence that stakeholders—including economic actors, communities, and institutions—have in the efficiency, fairness, and sustainability of the local economy.
5. **Regional/Local Cultural Aspects:** The influence of local beliefs, values, and behaviours on sustainable consumption, production, and waste practices, reflecting community attitudes toward CE.
6. **CE Citizenship Participation:** The active involvement of citizens in CE initiatives and campaigns, reinforcing the transition through widespread public engagement.

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2.3 Governance Dimension

The Governance Dimension examines the effectiveness of governance structures and stakeholder collaboration in enabling a circular economy (CE) transition. This dimension includes the following factors:

1. **Promotion of CE Culture and Trust:** Initiatives by local governments to foster a cultural shift toward sustainable practices, building confidence among stakeholders in the transition to CE.
2. **Dialogue Promotion in Decision-Making:** Encouraging collaboration across sectors (quintuple helix model) and including private actors in the policy-making process to create more inclusive CE strategies.
3. **Effective Multi-Level Governance:** Ensuring coordination and synergy across various levels of government to avoid working in silos, facilitating cohesive policy actions for CE.
4. **Adoption of a Functional Approach:** Promoting interconnectivity between urban and rural areas, fostering community-based initiatives, and identifying opportunities for industrial and urban symbiosis to enhance resource efficiency.
5. **Holistic Regional Systemic Approach:** Implementing long-term strategies that integrate circular models within government, aligned with CE objectives through clear goals and sustained political commitment.

2.4 Policy & Regulatory Dimension

The Policy & Regulatory Dimension addresses the legislative and regulatory framework needed to promote a circular economy (CE) by ensuring that policies facilitate sustainable practices and efficient resource use. Key factors in this dimension are:

1. **Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP):** The existence of a CEAP that provides a strategic roadmap, with defined targets and actions, guiding the region or city toward circularity.
2. **Adapted Regulatory Instruments:** Policies, laws, and regulations at the regional or local level that are tailored to support and accelerate the shift toward circular economic practices.
3. **Secondary Raw Materials Market:** The establishment of a regulated market that certifies recycled materials, ensuring quality, safety, and compliance with EU standards, promoting the use of secondary materials.

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4. **Effective Legislation Implementation:** The ability of regional or local authorities to not only implement but enforce legislation effectively, avoiding excessive bureaucracy and ensuring the intended environmental and economic outcomes.

2.5 Funding & Financial Dimension

The Funding & Financial Dimension evaluates the availability and effectiveness of financial resources and incentives that support circular economy (CE) initiatives at the regional and local levels. This dimension includes the following factors:

1. **Dedicated Financial Lines for CE Projects:** The presence of specific funding channels or instruments established by governments, financial institutions, or other entities to support projects advancing CE principles.
2. **Economic Instruments for Behavioural Change:** Financial mechanisms—such as tax incentives, environmental taxes, or differentiated tariffs—that encourage sustainable behaviours and discourage unsustainable practices within the community.
3. **Transparent Disclosure and Coordination of Funding Opportunities:** Clear and accessible information on available financial resources, along with strategic alignment of funding opportunities, ensuring that stakeholders can effectively access and leverage funding for CE initiatives.

This dimension underscores the necessity of financial backing and incentives to advance CE projects. By establishing dedicated funds, promoting behaviour-aligned incentives, and ensuring transparency, regions and cities can drive resource-efficient practices that support the overall transition to a circular economy.

2.6 Technology, Research & Innovation Dimension

The Technology, Research & Innovation Dimension assesses the scientific and technological capabilities required to support circular economy (CE) practices, focusing on innovation, infrastructure, and collaboration. The key factors are:

1. **Availability of Valorisation Technologies:** The presence of technologies and infrastructure for the valorisation of waste and byproducts, such as reuse and upcycling processes that enable efficient resource recovery.
2. **Public Investment in R&D:** The existence of public funding mechanisms dedicated to research and development in CE, fostering innovation at the regional or local level.
3. **Research-Industry Connection:** Strong linkages between research institutions and industry, which drive practical applications of CE innovations and enhance regional competitiveness.
4. **Participation of SMEs in R&D:** Engagement of small and medium-sized enterprises in research and development activities related to CE, promoting diverse and innovative solutions.

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5. **Product and Process Traceability:** Implementation of tools that improve the traceability of products and processes, ensuring transparency and accountability within the circular economy.
6. **Local R&D Funding Availability:** Access to regional or local resources for R&D that are mobilized specifically to support CE initiatives.

This dimension emphasizes the essential role of technology and innovation in advancing circular practices. Public investment, industry collaboration, and support for SMEs create a robust foundation for sustainable advancements, while traceability tools enhance transparency across value chains.

2.7 Standardisation Dimension

The Standardisation Dimension evaluates the extent to which a region or city adopts and implements standardized practices and certifications aligned with European Union standards to advance a circular economy (CE). This dimension includes the following factors:

1. **Creation of EU-Aligned Standards and Norms:** Active support for developing and adopting EU-wide standards for products made from secondary materials, ensuring quality, safety, and environmental compliance within the CE.
2. **Digital Tools for Product Traceability:** Adoption and promotion of standardized digital tools that improve the traceability of products and processes, making it easier to track materials and assess their sustainability.

This dimension highlights the importance of harmonized standards and traceability in supporting CE initiatives. By aligning with EU standards, regions foster consistency, reduce risks like greenwashing, and build public trust, while digital traceability tools ensure accountability and streamline CE operations across the value chain.

2.8 Capacity Building Dimension

The Capacity Building Dimension assesses a region's or city's ability to develop the necessary skills, knowledge, and workforce alignment to support circular economy (CE) initiatives. This dimension includes the following factors:

1. **Education System's Capacity for CE:** The extent to which the regional or local education system equips individuals with skills, knowledge, and technical expertise essential for addressing CE challenges.
2. **Alignment of Labour Supply and Demand in CE Sectors:** Ensuring that the local workforce supply meets the specific needs of CE industries, promoting a balanced match that supports sustainable economic growth.

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